

A Framework for Inconsistency-tolerant Reasoning with Sets of Models

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Abstract

We propose a framework for reasoning from inconsistent knowledge bases using minimal *hitting sets*, i. e., sets of interpretations such that each formula of the knowledge base is satisfied by at least one those interpretations. By additionally considering preference orders over minimal hitting sets, we can define a wide variety of non-monotonic inference relations. We consider concrete preference orders based on set inclusion, cardinality, the number of conflicting atoms within the hitting set, and using the Hamming distance between pairs of interpretations. We compare the resulting inference relations, characterize their logical properties, and position them relative to classical inference from maximal consistent subsets. Finally, we show that inference based on minimal conflicting atoms coincides with reasoning in Priest’s 3-valued logic.

1 Introduction

A core objective in knowledge representation and reasoning (KRR) is to support sound and meaningful inference from knowledge bases (Harmelen, Lifschitz, and Porter 2007). Inconsistencies are an unavoidable reality in large-scale, heterogeneous, or evolving knowledge bases. Whether arising from data integration, imperfect information, or conflicting sources, such inconsistencies pose a significant challenge for KRR systems. Considerable research has addressed methods for identifying and resolving them, including approaches from inconsistency measurement (Thimm 2018), belief revision (Fermé and Wassermann 2018), or ontology engineering (Kalyanpur et al. 2006; Baader et al. 2018). However, resolving inconsistencies may be difficult or undesirable—either due to the cost of modification or the need to preserve original information. In such cases, reasoning directly under inconsistency becomes essential (Rescher and Manor 1970; Benferhat, Dubois, and Prade 1997; Lang and Marquis 2010).

Traditional approaches to inconsistency-tolerant reasoning often rely on syntactic repairs, such as extracting maximal consistent subsets or applying belief revision operators. While these methods have proven effective in many contexts, they frequently ignore the semantic structure of the underlying models and treat all formulas uniformly, irrespective of their role in the inconsistency. Moreover, existing semantic

approaches typically lack mechanisms for flexible inference or fine-grained preference among models.

In this paper, we propose a new framework for inconsistency-tolerant reasoning based on sets of models—specifically, minimal hitting sets of interpretations guided by preference relations. This semantic perspective enables reasoning directly over interpretations, allowing for a wide spectrum of inference relations that range from cautious to permissive, depending on how preferred hitting sets are selected. This establishes a unified perspective that not only captures existing approaches as special cases but also supports the principled design of new inference strategies.

Our contribution lays the semantic foundation for a general framework of inconsistency-tolerant reasoning with sets of models. Rather than committing to a single inference relation, the framework is parameterized by a preference relation over hitting sets. We formally identify the basic properties that preference relations must satisfy to ensure well-behaved inference.

Our main contributions are as follows:

- We introduce a general framework for non-monotonic inference from inconsistent knowledge bases using minimal hitting sets of interpretations.
- We instantiate the framework using preference orders based on set inclusion, cardinality, conflicting atoms, and Hamming distance.
- We relate our framework to established approaches, including inference from maximal consistent subsets and reasoning in 3-valued logic.
- We define semantic conditions on preference relations that guarantee classical behavior for consistent knowledge and support principled non-monotonic inference under inconsistency.

Detailed proofs of all propositions and theorems are provided in the appendix of this paper.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides the necessary background on propositional logic and classical inference. In Section 3, we introduce our general framework for reasoning with minimal hitting sets. Section 4 presents various instantiations of preference orders and defines the resulting inference relations. Section 5

analyzes their relationships to inference from maximal consistent subsets and 3-valued logic. Section 6 shows the satisfaction of the non-monotonic properties of these inference modes. We conclude in Section 7 with a summary and directions for future research.

2 Background

Let At be some fixed propositional signature, i.e., a (possibly infinite) set of propositional variables (also called atoms), and let $\mathcal{L}(\text{At})$ be the corresponding propositional language constructed using the usual connectives \wedge (*conjunction*), \vee (*disjunction*), \rightarrow (*implication*), \leftrightarrow (*biconditional*) and \neg (*negation*). Furthermore, \top denotes an arbitrary tautology and \perp denotes an arbitrary contradiction.

If ϕ is a formula, we write $\text{At}(\phi)$ to denote the set of propositions appearing in ϕ . Similarly, for a set $\Phi = \{\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n\}$, we write $\text{At}(\Phi)$ for the propositions appearing in Φ . Furthermore, let $\bigwedge \Phi = \phi_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \phi_n$ and $\neg \Phi = \{\neg \phi \mid \phi \in \Phi\}$.

Semantics to a propositional language are given by *interpretations* where an *interpretation* ω on At is a function $\omega : \text{At} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$. Let $\Omega(\text{At})$ denote the set of all interpretations for At . An interpretation ω *satisfies* (or is a *model* of) an atom $a \in \text{At}$, denoted by $\omega \models a$, if and only if $\omega(a) = \text{true}$. The relation \models is extended to formulas in the usual way. For a set of formulas $\Phi \subseteq \mathcal{L}(\text{At})$ we write $\omega \models \Phi$ if $\omega \models \phi$ for every $\phi \in \Phi$. As an abbreviation we sometimes identify an interpretation ω with its complete conjunction i.e., if $a_1, \dots, a_n \in \text{At}$ are those propositional variables that are assigned true by ω and $a_{n+1}, \dots, a_m \in \text{At}$ are those variables that are assigned false by ω we identify ω by $a_1 \dots a_n \bar{a}_{n+1} \dots \bar{a}_m$ (or any permutation of this). For example, the interpretation ω_1 on $\{a, b, c\}$ with $\omega_1(a) = \omega_1(c) = \text{true}$ and $\omega_1(b) = \text{false}$ is abbreviated by $\bar{a}bc$. As usual, we use \models to denote classical entailment. That is, $\Phi \models \phi \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{L}(\text{At})) \times \mathcal{L}(\text{At})$, which is a binary relation, where $\Phi \models \phi$ if and only if every interpretation that satisfies Φ must also satisfy ϕ . In the following, let Φ, Φ_1, Φ_2 be sets of formulas. Define the set of models $\text{Mod}(\Phi) = \{\omega \in \Omega(\text{At}) \mid \omega \models \Phi\}$. We write $\Phi_1 \models \Phi_2$ if $\text{Mod}(\Phi_1) \subseteq \text{Mod}(\Phi_2)$. We say that Φ_1, Φ_2 are *equivalent*, denoted by $\Phi_1 \equiv \Phi_2$, if $\text{Mod}(\Phi_1) = \text{Mod}(\Phi_2)$. If $\text{Mod}(\Phi) = \emptyset$ holds, we say that Φ is *inconsistent*.

In this work, we are only considering knowledge bases that are non-empty and do not contain formulas that contradict themselves.

Definition 1. A knowledge base K is a non-empty finite set of formulas $K \subseteq \mathcal{L}(\text{At})$, such that $K \neq \emptyset$ and, every formula $\phi \in K$ is consistent. Let \mathbb{K} be the set of all knowledge bases.

Note that while every formula in the knowledge base K is consistent, the knowledge base itself can be inconsistent, for example $K = \{p, q, \neg p \vee \neg q\}$.

An important concept for reasoning under inconsistency is reasoning based on maximal consistent sets.

Definition 2. Let K be a knowledge base. A set $M \subseteq K$ is a *maximal consistent subset* of K if $M \not\models \perp$ and for all

$M' \subsetneq M$ holds $M' \models \perp$. With $\text{MCS}(K)$ we denote the set of all maximally consistent subsets of K .

Maximal consistent subsets provide a foundation for defining inference relations in the presence of inconsistency. We now recall two such classical inference relations introduced by Rescher and Manor 1970

Definition 3 (Rescher and Manor 1970). Let K be a knowledge base.

- A formula ϕ is said to be an *inevitable consequence* of K , shortly $K \sim_i^{\text{mc}} \phi$, if $M \models \phi$ for all $M \in \text{MCS}(K)$.
- A formula ϕ is said to be an *weak consequence* of K , shortly $K \sim_w^{\text{mc}} \phi$, if $M \models \phi$ for some $M \in \text{MCS}(K)$.

The following example clarifies Definition 2 and shows inference is possible from maximally consistent subsets.

Example 1. Consider the knowledge base $K = \{p, q, r \wedge \neg p\}$. First, observe that K is inconsistent. Note that $\text{MCS}(K) = \{\{p, q\}, \{q, r \wedge \neg p\}\}$ are the maximally consistent subsets of K . Hence, inevitable inference are some inferences are $K \sim_i^{\text{mc}} q$, and some weak consequence are $K \sim_w^{\text{mc}} p$, $K \sim_w^{\text{mc}} q$, $\sim_w^{\text{mc}} \neg p$, $K \sim_w^{\text{mc}} r$:

While inference based on maximal consistent subsets is a classical approach to reasoning under inconsistency, it does not take into account the semantic roles of individual formulas. For example, consider a formula such as r that is not directly involved in any contradiction. Despite this, it may be inferred with the same inference operator as p or $\neg p$ which are explicitly in conflict. This uniform treatment can obscure the distinction between formulas that merely coexist with inconsistency and those that contribute to it.

We now turn to Priest's 3-valued logic (Priest 1979), which extends classical truth values with a third option: both. This value represents cases where a formula is considered simultaneously true and false, capturing contradictions directly within the semantic evaluation.

Definition 4. A 3-valued interpretation ν on At is a function $\nu : \text{At} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}, \text{both}\}$.

The additional truth value *both* refers to the conflicting state when an atom is both *true* and *false* at the same time. The function ν is extended to formulas as shown in Table 1.

Definition 5. For a 3-valued interpretation ν and a formula ϕ , we write $\nu \models^3 \phi$ iff $\nu(\phi) \in \{\text{true}, \text{both}\}$. Let $\text{Mod}^3(K)$ be the set of all 3-valued models of the knowledge base K .

The relation \models^3 is extended naturally to sets of formulas: a 3-valued interpretation satisfies a set if it satisfies each individual formula in the set. For clarity, we use the symbol ν for 3-valued interpretations and the symbol ω for classical two-valued interpretations.

A 3-valued interpretation that assigns many atoms to *both* is not informative, as it often fails to yield a definitive truth value for many formulas. An illustrative extreme case is the interpretation ν_0 such that $\nu_0(a) = \text{both}$ for all $a \in \text{At}$, which is a model of every formula. Thus, we define a notion of minimal models for a knowledge base that minimizes the set of atoms assigned *both*.

$v(\phi)$	$v(\psi)$	$v(\phi \wedge \psi)$	$v(\phi \vee \psi)$	$v(\neg\phi)$
false	false	false	false	true
false	both	false	both	true
false	true	false	true	true
both	false	false	both	both
both	both	both	both	both
both	true	both	true	both
true	false	false	true	false
true	both	both	true	false
true	true	true	true	false

Table 1: 3-valued interpretation truth tables.

Definition 6. A model v of a knowledge base K is a minimal model of K if there is no other $v' \models^3 K$ with $(v')^{-1}(\text{both}) \subsetneq (v)^{-1}(\text{both})$. Let $\text{MinMod}^3(K)$ denote the set of minimal models of K .

Based on Definition 6, we define an inference relation that considers only such minimal models.

Definition 7. Define the 3-valued inference relation \vdash^3 via

$$K \vdash^3 \phi \text{ iff } v \models^3 \phi \text{ for every } v \in \text{MinMod}^3(K).$$

Having reviewed both classical and 3-valued approaches to reasoning under inconsistency, we now turn to our hitting set-based framework, which builds on sets of interpretations to support a flexible and semantically grounded inference mechanism.

3 A General framework for Reasoning with Hitting Sets

In this section, we introduce a framework for inconsistency-tolerant reasoning built upon the concept of *hitting sets* of interpretations. This approach allows us to define inference relations that operate directly on sets of models, providing a more fine-grained and adaptable foundation for drawing conclusions from potentially conflicting information. We consider the following definition of a hitting set (Thimm 2016; Thimm 2014).

Definition 8. Let K be a knowledge base. A set $H \subseteq \Omega(\text{At})$ is a *hitting set* of K , if for all $\phi \in K$ there is $\omega \in H$ with $\omega \models \phi$. Let $\mathcal{H}(K)$ be the set of all hitting sets of K .¹

Hitting sets were originally introduced as a tool for measuring inconsistency in knowledge bases (Thimm 2016; Thimm 2014).

Consider the following example.

Example 2. Given the knowledge base $K_1 = \{p, \neg p \wedge q\}$. It has the following hitting sets:

$$\mathcal{H}(K_1) = \{\{pq, \bar{p}q\}, \{p\bar{q}, \bar{p}q\}, \{pq, \bar{p}\bar{q}, \bar{p}q\}, \\ \{pq, p\bar{q}, \bar{p}q\}, \{p\bar{q}, \bar{p}q, \bar{p}\bar{q}\}, \{pq, \bar{p}\bar{q}, \bar{p}q, p\bar{q}\}\}$$

¹Note that in a more general sense, a set H is a *hitting set* of a set of sets S if $M \cap T \neq \emptyset$ for all $T \in S$. In our context, S is a set of formulas and each formula is represented by its set of models. So a hitting set H of a knowledge base K is the same as a hitting set of $\{\text{Mod}(\phi) \mid \phi \in K\}$.

Although any set of interpretations that satisfies every formula in the knowledge base qualifies as a hitting set, many such sets may contain redundant or unnecessary elements. For instance, in Example 2, the set $pq, \bar{p}q$ is sufficient to satisfy the knowledge base, but larger sets are still technically valid hitting sets. To refine this notion for inference, we introduce preference relations over hitting sets to isolate those that are minimal in a well-defined sense.

We generalize the notion of minimality by considering minimality with respect to an arbitrary relation \prec over hitting sets.

Definition 9. Given a knowledge base K . A hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}(K)$ is *minimal* wrt. $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ if there is no $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K)$ with $H' \prec H$. Let $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ denote the set of all minimal hitting sets of K wrt. \prec .

The idea of minimality depends on the specific preference relation \prec applied. This flexibility allows us to tailor inference to different intuitions about what constitutes a "better" or "more informative" set of interpretations. In the next definition, we formalize four distinct modes of inference by quantifying over both preferred hitting sets and the interpretations they contain.

Definition 10. For $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$, define inference relations $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}}, \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}}, \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}}$ and $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}}$ via

$$\begin{aligned} K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \phi & \text{ if } \forall H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K) : \forall \omega \in H : \omega \models \phi \\ K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \phi & \text{ if } \forall H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \models \phi \\ K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi & \text{ if } \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K) : \forall \omega \in H : \omega \models \phi \\ K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi & \text{ if } \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \models \phi \end{aligned}$$

for every knowledge base K and formula ϕ .

- If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \phi$ holds, we say that ϕ is a *necessary skeptical inference* of K (wrt. \prec).
- If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \phi$ holds, we say that ϕ is a *necessary credulous inference* of K (wrt. \prec).
- If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi$ holds, we say that ϕ is a *possible skeptical inference* of K (wrt. \prec).
- If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi$ holds, we say that ϕ is a *possible credulous inference* of K (wrt. \prec).

These four inference relations offer different perspectives on reasoning from sets of models. Necessary inferences (both skeptical and credulous) require that a formula holds across all minimal hitting sets, differing on whether every interpretation (skeptical) or some interpretation (credulous) within the hitting set must satisfy the formula. Possible inferences, in contrast, require only the existence of a minimal hitting set where the formula holds universally (skeptical) or partially (credulous). This distinction allows flexible reasoning patterns, depending on how cautious or permissive one wishes to be when accepting conclusions from possibly inconsistent knowledge bases.

Not every preference relation yields meaningful inference. In particular, we want to ensure that minimal hitting sets exist and that the framework aligns with classical logic when

the knowledge base is consistent. To that end, we identify two critical properties for preference relations—well-foundedness and compatibility with classical consistency—and define proper relations as those that satisfy both. These ensure that our inference is well-behaved in both consistent and inconsistent cases.

Definition 11. Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation. We say that $S \subseteq 2^\Omega$ is *well-founded* by T if $T \in S$ and there is no $T' \in S$ such that $T' \prec T$. We say that \prec is *well-founded* for S if S is well-founded by some $T \in S$. If \prec is well-founded for all $S \subseteq 2^\Omega$, then we say that \prec is *well-founded*.

In order to ensure that inference from inconsistent knowledge bases behaves in accordance with classical logic, it is essential to impose additional constraints on preference relations. One such constraint is *compatibility with classical consistency*, which requires that, in the absence of inconsistency, the framework reproduce the standard semantics of classical entailment. Intuitively, this means that when the knowledge base is consistent, every model of the knowledge base should be represented by a singleton minimal hitting set. This condition provides a bridge between non-monotonic reasoning in the presence of inconsistency and classical reasoning when no inconsistency is present.

Definition 12. Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation. We say \prec is *compatible with classical consistency* if for every consistent knowledge base K the following holds:

- every $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is a singleton, and
- $\bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)} H = \text{Mod}(K)$.

We define a preference relation $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ as proper if it is well-founded and compatible with classical consistency.

Definition 13. A relation $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ is called *proper* if it is well-founded and compatible with classical consistency.

The next proposition shows that for a well-founded relation, the set of minimal hitting sets is non-empty for every knowledge base.

Proposition 1. Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation and let K be a knowledge base. The following statements hold:

- If \prec is well-founded, then $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is non-empty.
- Each $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is non-empty.

When the preference relation is proper, we can ensure that our inference relations agree with classical entailment whenever the knowledge base is consistent. The next result confirms that both necessary skeptical and necessary credulous inference collapse to classical inference in such cases.

Corollary 1. Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation, let K be a consistent knowledge base, and let ϕ be a formula. If \prec is compatible with classical consistency, then $K \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} \phi$ iff $K \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} \phi$ iff $K \models \phi$.

For consistent knowledge bases, the possible inference relations align with classical reasoning in a weaker manner. More precisely, they ensure that any inferred formula remains consistent with the original knowledge base.

Corollary 2. Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation, K be a consistent knowledge base, and ϕ a formula. If \prec is compatible with classical consistency, then $K \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} \phi$ iff $K \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} \phi$ iff $K \cup \{\phi\} \not\models \perp$.

Together, these results establish proper preference relations as a foundation for well-behaved inference. They guarantee the existence of minimal hitting sets and ensure that, in the absence of inconsistency, the framework faithfully reproduces classical reasoning.

In the following, we instantiate different minimality criteria, highlighting their ability in prioritizing relevant interpretations and hitting sets for effective inference.

4 Instantiation of Minimality in Inference Relations

In the following subsections, we will instantiate the general framework from Definition 10 with 4 different approaches for \prec and analyse the properties of the resulting inference relations.

4.1 Inference from Minimal Set Inclusion Hitting Sets

As a starting point, we consider minimizing hitting sets with respect to set inclusion.²

Definition 14. Define $\prec_{se} \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ via $H \prec_{se} H'$ iff $H \subsetneq H'$, for all $H, H' \subseteq 2^\Omega$.

We illustrate in the following example how set-inclusion minimality can lead to questionable inferences.

Example 3. The knowledge base $K_2 = \{p, q\}$ will have the minimal hitting sets $\mathcal{H}_{\prec_{se}}(K_2) = \{\{pq\}, \{p\bar{q}\}, \{\bar{p}q\}\}$. Hence, we obtain the inferences $K_2 \vdash_{\prec_{se}}^{pc} \neg p$, $K_2 \vdash_{\prec_{se}}^{pc} \neg q$.

Although intuitive and widely adopted, set-inclusion minimality does not preserve desirable logical behavior. In particular, it fails to ensure compatibility with classical inference, even when the knowledge base is consistent. Consequently, the relation \prec_{se} is not proper.

Proposition 2. The relation \prec_{se} does not satisfy compatibility with classical consistency.

This example demonstrates the failure of compatibility with classical consistency under set-inclusion minimality. As a result, the guarantees provided by Corollaries 1, 2 no longer apply. Notably, the inference mechanism permits the derivation of formulas such as $\neg p$ which, when added back to the knowledge base, would reintroduce inconsistency. Because of this, we will not further consider inference relations based on \prec_{se} .

4.2 Inference from Cardinality Minimal Hitting Sets

Next, we consider cardinality-based minimality, where preference is given to hitting sets containing the smallest number of interpretations. This approach aims to capture a form of parsimony in model selection. From this point forward, all

²The subscript “se” stands for set inclusion.

minimality criteria we consider will be compatible with classical consistency.

Definition 15. Define $\prec_{\#} \subseteq 2^{\Omega} \times 2^{\Omega}$ via $H \prec_{\#} H'$ iff $|H| < |H'|$, for all $H, H' \subseteq 2^{\Omega}$.

For convenience, we use $\mathcal{H}_{\#}(K)$ as an abbreviation for $\mathcal{H}_{\prec_{\#}}(K)$. Similarly, we abbreviate the corresponding relations $\vdash_{\prec_{\#}}^{\text{ns}}, \vdash_{\prec_{\#}}^{\text{nc}}, \vdash_{\prec_{\#}}^{\text{ps}}$, and $\vdash_{\prec_{\#}}^{\text{pc}}$ as $\vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}}, \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}}, \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}}$, and $\vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}}$, respectively.

To ensure that cardinality-based inference is well-defined and logically aligned with classical reasoning, we verify that this preference relation satisfies the conditions for being proper.

Proposition 3. *The relation $\prec_{\#}$ is proper.*

This implies that all minimal hitting sets under cardinality have the same size, which reinforces the regularity of the selection criterion.

Observation 1. *Let K be a consistent knowledge base. For all $H, H' \in \mathcal{H}_{\#}(K)$, it holds $|H| = |H'|$.*

Although cardinality-based minimality respects classical consistency, it does not control the internal diversity of interpretations within a hitting set. As a result, the inferred conclusions may still be counterintuitive or misleading, as illustrated next.

Example 4. Consider the knowledge base $K_3 = \{p, \neg p \wedge r, q\}$. It contains the following cardinality minimal hitting sets:

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= \{pqr, \bar{p}qr\}, H_2 = \{pqr, \bar{p}\bar{q}r\}, H_3 = \{pq\bar{r}, \bar{p}qr\}, \\ H_4 &= \{pq\bar{r}, \bar{p}\bar{q}r\}, H_5 = \{p\bar{q}\bar{r}, \bar{p}qr\}, \text{ and } H_6 = \{p\bar{q}r, \bar{p}qr\} \\ \mathcal{H}_{\#}(K_3) &= \{H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5, H_6\} \end{aligned}$$

Now consider the formulas $p \vee r$, $\neg p$, $q \wedge r$, $\neg q$ and $p \wedge r$. One can observe the following:

1. $K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}} p \vee r$, since all interpretation in each minimal hitting set in $\mathcal{H}_{\#}(K_3)$ satisfy $p \vee r$
2. $K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}} \neg p$, since in every minimal hitting set in $\mathcal{H}_{\#}(K_3)$ there is an ω that models $\neg p$.
3. $K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}} q \wedge r$, since both interpretations of H_1 model $q \wedge r$.
4. $K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}} \neg q$, since there exist an interpretation in a hitting set that model $\neg q$, like the first interpretation in H_5 .
5. $K_3 \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}} \neg p$, because there is some interpretation (like $\bar{p}qr$ in H_1) that does not model $\neg p$
6. $K_3 \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}} q \wedge r$, because there is some hitting set H_4 where all interpretations does not model $q \wedge r$
7. $K_3 \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}} \neg p$ because for every minimal hitting set there will always be some interpretation that satisfies p since it exists as formula in the knowledge base.
8. $K_3 \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}} p \wedge r$ since no interpretation satisfies $p \wedge r$

Figure 1 summarizes the entailment of $\vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}}, \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}}, \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}}$, and $\vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}}$.

Note that the inference $K \vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}} \neg q$ is obtained. This outcome is arguably problematic because q is explicitly contained in the knowledge base, yet the cardinality inference framework allows deriving its negation. Furthermore, the formula q is not entailed under necessary skeptical inference, despite being unrelated to the inconsistency.

Formula	$K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}}$	$K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}}$	$K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}}$	$K_3 \vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}}$
$p \vee r$	✓	✓	✓	✓
$\neg p$	✗	✓	✗	✓
$q \wedge r$	✗	✗	✓	✓
$\neg q$	✗	✗	✗	✓
$p \wedge r$	✗	✗	✗	✗

Figure 1: Entailment of $\vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}}, \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}}, \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}}$, and $\vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}}$ for the knowledge base $K_3 = \{p, \neg p \wedge r, q\}$ and the formulas from Example 4.

4.3 Inference from Minimal Conflicting Atoms Hitting Sets

Cardinality-based minimality minimizes the number of interpretations but not the differences between them. As a result, interpretations within a minimal hitting set may disagree on many atoms, which can lead to problematic inferences. To mitigate this, we introduce a new minimality criterion that penalizes such internal disagreement by minimizing the number of conflicting truth assignments across interpretations.

Definition 16. Let $H \subseteq \Omega$ be a set of interpretations. Define the set of *conflicting atoms* $CA(H)$ of H as

$$CA(H) = \{a \mid \exists \omega, \omega' \in H \text{ such that } \omega(a) \neq \omega'(a)\}$$

In other words $a \in CA(H)$ iff there are two interpretations in H that differ on their truth values of a . Using $CA(H)$ leads to a preference relation that ranks hitting sets by the set of atoms on which interpretations disagree.

Definition 17. Define³ $\prec_{ca} \subseteq 2^{\Omega} \times 2^{\Omega}$ via $H \prec_{ca} H'$ iff $CA(H) \subsetneq CA(H')$, for any $H, H' \in 2^{\Omega}$.

To illustrate the difference between cardinality and conflicting-atoms minimality, we revisit the earlier knowledge base K_3 from Example 4. This comparison highlights how conflicting-atoms minimization avoids some of the un-intuitive conclusions permitted by the cardinality criterion.

Example 5. In comparison to minimal cardinality hitting sets, the variation between interpretations in hitting sets decreases drastically. The minimal conflicting atoms hitting sets for K_3 are:

$$\mathcal{H}_{ca}(K_3) = \{\{pqr, \bar{p}qr\}\}$$

and therefore $\neg q$ is not entailed by any of the inference relations, while q is inferred by all of them.

As with previous criteria, we check whether the conflicting-atoms preference relation satisfies the requirements of being proper — namely, whether it guarantees minimal hitting sets and aligns with classical inference in the consistent case.

Proposition 4. *The relation \prec_{ca} is proper.*

The property established above guarantees that for consistent knowledge bases, minimal hitting sets under conflicting atoms minimality criterion are singletons and therefore behave consistently with classical inference.

³The subscript “ca” stands for *conflicting atoms*.

4.4 Inference from Minimal Hamming Distance Hitting sets

We now consider another way to measure variation among interpretations in a hitting set, the Hamming distance (Also known as Dalal distance). Unlike \prec_{ca} , which considers the set of atoms where interpretations differ, Hamming distance quantifies the degree of such differences by summing pairwise discrepancies.

Definition 18. Define the Hamming distance $d : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ as

$$d(\omega, \omega') = |\{a \in \text{At} \mid \omega(a) \neq \omega'(a)\}|$$

for all $\omega, \omega' \in \Omega(\text{At})$. For a set $X \subseteq \Omega$ we write

$$D(X) = \sum_{\omega_1, \omega_2 \in X} d(\omega_1, \omega_2)$$

We extend the Hamming distance to sets of interpretations by summing all pairwise distances. This aggregate measure reflects the overall dissimilarity within a hitting set and underpins a preference for sets with greater internal coherence.

Definition 19. Define⁴ $\prec_d \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ via $H \prec_d H'$ iff $D(H) < D(H')$, for any $H, H' \subseteq 2^\Omega$.

This ordering selects hitting sets with minimal total pairwise disagreement across interpretations. Unlike \prec_{ca} , the Hamming distance takes into account the degree of disagreement, not just its presence. As the next example shows, the two criteria are incomparable, i. e., neither strictly subsumes the other.

Example 6. Let $K = \{p \wedge q \wedge r, p \rightarrow q \wedge \neg r, \neg q \wedge \neg r\}$. Consider the following hitting sets:

$$\begin{array}{ll} H_1 = \{pqr, \bar{p}\bar{q}\bar{r}\} & H_2 = \{pqr, p\bar{q}\bar{r}, p\bar{q}r\} \\ D(H_1) = 6 & D(H_2) = 8 \\ CA(H_1) = \{p, q, r\} & CA(H_2) = \{q, r\} \end{array}$$

Notice in Example 6 that $H_1 \in \mathcal{H}_d(K)$ and $H_1 \notin \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$. Hence, $\mathcal{H}_d(K) \not\subseteq \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$. Similarly for the other direction, $H_2 \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$ and $H_2 \notin \mathcal{H}_d(K)$.

As with earlier criteria, we confirm that the Hamming distance ordering is proper.

Proposition 5. The relation \prec_d is proper.

To conclude, Hamming-distance minimality provides another perspective on disagreements between interpretations by quantifying the total number of differing atomic assignments. Like the cardinality and conflicting-atoms approaches, it satisfies the basic properties of well-foundedness and compatibility with classical consistency. This ensures that the resulting inference relations are proper and maintain classical behavior for consistent knowledge bases, while enabling a refined form of inference under inconsistency.

⁴The subscript “d” stands for *Dalal*.

Figure 2: Relationship among \sim_{\prec}^{ns} , \sim_{\prec}^{nc} , \sim_{\prec}^{ps} , \sim_{\prec}^{pc} for an arbitrary \prec , given that \prec is well-founded. Arrow directions indicate the antecedent to consequent relation.

5 Relationships Among Inference Relations

In this section, we analyze how the four hitting-based inference relations— \sim_{\prec}^{ns} , \sim_{\prec}^{nc} , \sim_{\prec}^{ps} , and \sim_{\prec}^{pc} —relate to each other and to existing approaches, including inference from maximal consistent subsets and Priest’s 3-valued logic. Understanding these relationships helps position our framework within the broader landscape of nonmonotonic reasoning and highlights the inferential strengths and limitations of each mode.

5.1 Relationships Among Hitting Sets Inference Relations

We begin by examining the relationships among the four inference types within our framework. Specifically, we identify which inference relations are strictly stronger than others and where no such containment holds. This comparative analysis clarifies how each inference mode varies in strength and independence.

We start with establishing general inclusion relationships among the four inference relations, abstracting away from any specific choice of ordering \prec .

Proposition 6. Let K be a knowledge base, and let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a well-founded relation. The following relationships among \sim_{\prec}^{ns} , \sim_{\prec}^{nc} , \sim_{\prec}^{ps} , and \sim_{\prec}^{pc} hold:

1. If $K \sim_{\prec}^{ns} \phi$, then $K \sim_{\prec}^{nc} \phi$
2. If $K \sim_{\prec}^{ns} \phi$, then $K \sim_{\prec}^{ps} \phi$
3. If $K \sim_{\prec}^{nc} \phi$, then $K \sim_{\prec}^{pc} \phi$
4. If $K \sim_{\prec}^{ps} \phi$, then $K \sim_{\prec}^{pc} \phi$

The next lemma captures the duality between necessary and possible inference, showing how negation interrelates the two modes.

Lemma 1. Let K be a knowledge base, ϕ a formula, and $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$. Then

- $K \sim_{\prec}^{ps} \phi$ iff $K \not\sim_{\prec}^{nc} \neg\phi$.
- $K \sim_{\prec}^{pc} \phi$ iff $K \not\sim_{\prec}^{ns} \neg\phi$.

We now present an example that illustrates how different inference relations can yield distinct conclusions, emphasizing their incomparability.

Example 7. Let $K = \{p \wedge q \wedge r \wedge s \wedge t, \neg(p \vee q \vee r \vee s \vee t) \vee (\neg p \wedge q \wedge r \wedge s \wedge t), \neg(p \vee q \vee r \vee s \vee t) \vee (p \wedge \neg q \wedge r \wedge s \wedge t)\}$ be a knowledge base. It will have the following hitting sets:

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= \{pqrst, \bar{p}qrst, p\bar{q}rst\} & H_2 &= \{pqrst, \bar{p}\bar{q}\bar{r}\bar{s}\bar{t}\} \\ \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K) &= \mathcal{H}_d(K) = \{H_1\} & \mathcal{H}_\#(K) &= \{H_2\} \end{aligned}$$

We say that two inference relations \vdash_x and \vdash_y are incomparable if there are K, K' and ϕ, ϕ' such that

$$K \vdash_x \phi \quad K \not\vdash_y \phi \quad K' \not\vdash_x \phi' \quad K' \vdash_y \phi'$$

The following proposition shows that inference relations considered in this paper, which are not covered by Proposition 6 are incomparable. That is, for distinct minimality relations, neither inference relation uniformly entails the other.

Proposition 7. For all $I \in \{ns, nc, ps, pc\}$, and all $(x, y) \in \{(\#, ca), (\#, d), (d, ca)\}$, the relations \vdash_x^I and \vdash_y^I are incomparable.

5.2 Relationship with Maximal Consistent Subsets Inference

We now compare our framework to inference based on maximal consistent subsets (\vdash_i^{mc} and \vdash_w^{mc}), as introduced by Rescher and Manor (Rescher and Manor 1970). In particular, we focus on how cardinality-minimal hitting sets relate to the maximally consistent subsets of a knowledge base. The intuition is that every maximally consistent subset corresponds to at least one interpretation in a cardinality-minimal hitting set. This correspondence is made precise in the following result.

Proposition 8. Let K be a knowledge base. Then

$$\forall M \in MCS(K) : \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_\#(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \models M$$

Thus, for each maximally consistent subset of the knowledge base, some interpretation in a cardinality-minimal hitting set satisfies it. This leads to the following theorem relating the respective inference notions.

Theorem 1. It holds:

1. $\vdash_\#^{ns} \subsetneq \vdash_i^{mc}$
2. $\vdash_w^{mc} \subsetneq \vdash_\#^{pc}$

This result situates our inference framework between the classical extremes. Necessary skeptical inference based on cardinality is more selective than Rescher and Manor's inevitable consequence, while possible credulous inference is more permissive than their weak consequence.

5.3 Relationship with 3-valued Inference

In this section, we consider a variant of 3-valued inference that selects models which minimize the use of the indeterminate truth value (both), as showed in Definition 6. We then examine how this semantics corresponds to inference in our framework based on hitting sets that minimize conflicting atoms.

To connect our framework with 3-valued reasoning, we define a transformation from a hitting set of classical interpretations to a single 3-valued interpretation. This construction captures the agreement across interpretations directly, while encoding any disagreement as the value *both*.

Definition 20. Let K be a knowledge base and $H \in \mathcal{H}(K)$ a hitting set of K . The H -induced 3-valued interpretation v_H is the 3-valued interpretation v_H defined as

$$v_H(a) = \begin{cases} true & \text{if } \forall \omega \in H : \omega(a) = true \\ false & \text{if } \forall \omega \in H : \omega(a) = false \\ both & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for all $a \in At$.

By definition, any atom assigned *both* in the resulting 3-valued interpretation corresponds exactly to an atom with conflicting truth values across the hitting set.

Observation 2. For any knowledge base K , and an H -induced 3-valued interpretation v_H from some $H \in \mathcal{H}(K)$: it holds $CA(H) = v_H^{-1}(both)$.

Different 3-valued interpretations may provide varying levels of information, depending on how many atoms they assign determinately (as *true* or *false*) versus ambiguously (as *both*). To formalize this, we introduce an information ordering that compares interpretations based on their determinacy.

Definition 21. Let v, v' be a 3-valued interpretation. Define the *information order* \sqsubseteq via $v' \sqsubseteq v$ iff $v'(true)^{-1} \subseteq v(true)^{-1}$ and $v'(false)^{-1} \subseteq v(false)^{-1}$

Note that classical (two-valued) interpretations are maximal elements in this ordering, since they assign a definite truth value to every atom. Conversely, the interpretation mapping every atom to *both* is the least informative element.

Proposition 9. Let ϕ be a formula, and v, v' be 3-valued interpretations. For every $v' \sqsubseteq v$ it holds that

1. If $v(\phi) = true$, then $v'(\phi) \in \{true, both\}$
2. If $v(\phi) = both$, then $v'(\phi) = both$
3. If $v(\phi) = false$, then $v'(\phi) \in \{false, both\}$

The next result lifts the Proposition 9 from individual formulas to entire knowledge bases, showing that every H -induced 3-valued interpretation satisfies the original knowledge base.

Proposition 10. Let K be a knowledge base. Then for all $H \in \mathcal{H}(K)$, $v_H \models^3 K$.

Conversely, to complete the correspondence, we show the opposite direction of having a hitting set that can satisfy every formula in knowledge base K given that there exists a 3-valued interpretation $v \models^3 K$. We define next we introduce a construction that maps a 3-valued interpretation to a set of two-valued interpretations. This mapping reflects the idea that a 3-valued interpretation can be viewed as an abstraction over multiple classical interpretations. Specifically, we define the notion of v -induced hitting sets, which extract from a 3-valued interpretation those two-valued interpretations that agree with it on all determinate (non-'both') assignments.

Definition 22. Let v be a 3-valued interpretation. Define the v -induced hitting set H_v via

$$H_v = \{\omega \in \Omega(\text{At}) \mid v \sqsubseteq \omega\}$$

3-valued induced hitting set H_v corresponding to a 3-valued interpretation v preserves all deterministic truth assignments while introducing variation only for atoms assigned *both*. Specifically, for every atom a where $v(a) = \text{both}$, the hitting set must include at least two interpretations $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in H_v$ such that $\omega_1(a) = \text{true}$ and $\omega_2(a) = \text{false}$. As a result, the following is observed:

Observation 3. For any knowledge base K , and an v -induced hitting set H_v from some $v \models K$. It holds that $CA(H) = v_H^{-1}(\text{both})$.

Note that the relation \models^3 is invariant under certain classical equivalences, in particular De Morgan's law and distributivity rules.

Example 8. Given an interpretation $v \models^3 \neg(p \wedge q)$. Applying De Morgan's law to $\neg(p \wedge q)$ yields $\neg p \vee \neg q$. It is the case $v \models^3 \neg(p \wedge q)$ iff $v \models^3 \neg p \vee \neg q$.

Similarly, \models^3 is preserved under transformations such as associativity and distributivity of \vee and \wedge , as well as the rewriting of implications into disjunctions. This invariance justifies assuming, without loss of generality, that all formulas are given in conjunctive normal form (CNF).

To ensure that the subsequent results apply uniformly, we restrict attention to knowledge bases in CNF. The following proposition shows that this restriction does not affect the generality of our results.

Proposition 11. Let v be a 3-valued interpretation and let ϕ be a formula. It holds that $v \models^3 \phi$ iff $v \models^3 \phi'$, where ϕ' is an equivalent conjunctive normal form of ϕ .

As a first step toward establishing the equivalence between conflicting-atoms-based inference and 3-valued semantics, we consider the case of disjunctive formulas. The following lemma shows that if a 3-valued interpretation satisfies such a formula, then there exists a corresponding 2-valued interpretation—within the v -induced hitting set—that also satisfies the formula. This forms the basis for lifting satisfaction from 3-valued models to their classical refinements.

Lemma 2. Let ϕ be a clause and v a 3-valued interpretation with $v \models^3 \phi$. Then there is $\omega \in H_v$ with $\omega \models \phi$.

We now extend the previous result to full knowledge bases. The proposition shows that every 3-valued model of a knowledge base induces a hitting set of classical interpretations that together satisfy all formulas in the base.

Proposition 12. Let K be a knowledge base, where $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses, and v a 3-valued interpretation for K . If $v \models^3 K$ then $H_v \in \mathcal{H}(K)$.

We now extend the previous result to full knowledge bases. The proposition shows that every 3-valued model of a knowledge base induces a hitting set of classical interpretations that together satisfy all formulas in the base.

Proposition 13. Let K be a knowledge base, where $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses, and $v \in \text{MinMod}^3(K)$, then $H_v \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$.

We now establish the converse: every minimal hitting set under the conflicting-atoms preference induces a minimal 3-valued model. This bidirectional correspondence fully aligns the two approaches.

Proposition 14. Let K be a knowledge base where $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses. For each $H \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$, then $v_H \in \text{MinMod}^3(K)$.

In the following, we finally complete the equivalence between minimal conflicting-atoms hitting sets coincides with inference in Priest's 3-valued logic, provided the knowledge base is in conjunctive normal form. This result connects our semantic hitting set-based approach to a well-established non-classical logic for reasoning under inconsistency.

Theorem 2. Let K be a knowledge base such that $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses. $\Phi \sim^3 \phi$ iff $\Phi \sim_{ca}^{nc} \phi$

This correspondence demonstrates that the conflicting-atoms minimality criterion not only aligns with intuitive notions of disagreement in interpretations but also captures the semantics of an established many-valued logic. By bridging our hitting set-based framework with Priest's 3-valued logic, we provide a principled foundation for reasoning under inconsistency that combines the clarity of classical models with the flexibility of non-classical valuation.

6 KLM Properties for Inference with Minimal Conflicting Atoms

In this section, we examine how our hitting set-based inference relations behave when knowledge bases are extended. This is crucial for assessing whether the framework satisfies desirable nonmonotonic reasoning principles, such as those captured by the KLM postulates. We begin by analyzing how minimal hitting sets evolve when a consistent formula is added to a knowledge base.

Proposition 15. Let K be a knowledge base, let ϕ be a formula, and let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation. If there is a hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ with $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$. Then, there is no $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$, and $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K \cup \{\phi\})$.

To capture this behavior more generally, we introduce a property of preference relations called regularity. Intuitively, regularity ensures that if a formula is already satisfied within a minimal hitting set, then adding that formula to the knowledge base should not generate new, strictly preferred hitting sets.

Definition 23. Given a knowledge base K , and a consistent formula ϕ . A relation $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ is called *regular* if there exists some $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ with $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$, then $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K \cup \{\phi\}) \subseteq \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ holds.

Regularity requires a form of structural persistence in the preference relation: if a formula ψ holds in some minimal hitting set of a knowledge base K , then this hitting set must remain among the minimal ones after the formula is added. In other words, the existence of such a hitting set

$H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ ensures that all hitting sets $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K \cup \{\psi\})$ must satisfy the same preference constraints.

We now verify that the main preference relations considered in this paper—cardinality, conflicting atoms, and Hamming distance—all satisfy the regularity condition.

Proposition 16. *The relations $\prec_\#, \prec_{ca}$, and \prec_d are regular.*

We recall that regularity ensures a form of persistence: if a formula holds in some minimal hitting set of a knowledge base, then the inclusion of that formula in the knowledge base cannot introduce new strictly preferred hitting sets. The following propositions formalize this behavior.

Proposition 17. *Let K be a knowledge base, let ϕ be a consistent formula, and let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a regular relation. If a minimal hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ contains a model of ϕ , then $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K \cup \{\phi\}) \subseteq \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$.*

Next, we define the notion of hitting set equivalence, which characterizes when two knowledge bases yield the same collection of minimal hitting sets under a given preference relation.

Definition 24. Let K, K' be knowledge bases and $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$. We say the knowledge bases K and K' are hitting set equivalent, or $K \equiv_\prec^H K'$ if $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K) = \mathcal{H}_\prec(K')$

With the structural properties of preference relations in place, we now assess how our inference framework aligns with well-known nonmonotonic reasoning principles—mainly System P, as introduced by Kraus, Lehmann, and Magidor (Kraus, Lehmann, and Magidor 1990). The system encompasses several desirable principles for nonmonotonic reasoning, which we briefly recall below.

The following properties are mostly those of System P, but note that knowledge bases may not contain inconsistent formulas (yet the knowledge bases may be inconsistent at all):

- $\{\phi\} \sim \phi$. (Ref)
- If $\phi \models \psi$ and $K \sim \phi$, then $K \sim \psi$. (RW)
- If $K \equiv^H K'$ and $K \sim \phi$, then $K' \sim \phi$. (LLE)
- If $\psi, K \cup \{\psi\} \sim \phi$ and $K \sim \psi$, then $K \sim \phi$. (Cut)
- If $\psi, K \sim \psi$ and $K \sim \phi$, then $K \cup \{\psi\} \sim \phi$. (CM)
- If $\phi \sim \chi$ and $\psi \sim \chi$, then $\{\phi \vee \psi\} \sim \chi$. (Or)
- If $K \sim \phi$ and $K \not\sim \psi$, then $K \cup \{\psi\} \sim \phi$. (RM)

In the area of non-monotonic logic, System P is known as the conservative core of non-monotonic reasoning, as it captures preferential entailment (Kraus, Lehmann, and Magidor 1990); respectively, all properties of System P, except for the property Or, are known due to Gabbay as basic properties of non-monotonic inference relations (Gabbay 1984).

The following theorem summarizes which of the KLM postulates are satisfied by our inference relations, assuming the underlying preference relation is regular and proper. The result shows that the framework adheres to nearly all key principles of nonmonotonic reasoning. In particular, necessary inference relations satisfy all properties of System P, including cautious monotony, while possible inference relations fail this one condition, reflecting their more permissive nature.

	\sim_\prec^{ns}	\sim_\prec^{nc}	\sim_\prec^{ps}	\sim_\prec^{pc}
Ref	✓	✓	✓	✓
RW	✓	✓	✓	✓
LLE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cut	✓	✓	✓	✓
CM	✓	✓	✗	✗
Or	✓	✓	✓	✓
RM	✓	✓	✓	✓

Figure 3: Overview of the satisfaction (✓), respectively violation (✗), of inference properties by \sim_\prec^{ns} , \sim_\prec^{nc} , \sim_\prec^{ps} , and \sim_\prec^{pc} . For any regular proper relation $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$

Theorem 3. *Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a proper regular relation.*

- \sim_\prec^{ns} , \sim_\prec^{nc} , \sim_\prec^{ps} and \sim_\prec^{pc} satisfy Ref, RW, LLE, Cut, Or, and RM.
- \sim_\prec^{ns} , \sim_\prec^{nc} satisfy CM
- \sim_\prec^{ps} , \sim_\prec^{pc} violate CM

This analysis confirms that our framework supports robust nonmonotonic reasoning when instantiated with regular proper preference relations. The necessary inference modes, in particular, satisfy all of the core KLM postulates, including cautious monotony, thereby aligning with the foundational principles of preferential entailment. While the possible inference modes trade some logical discipline for flexibility, their behavior remains well-characterized within the framework. Overall, these results underscore the expressive power and formal soundness of hitting set-based inference under appropriately constrained preference relations.

7 Concluding Remarks

We have introduced a general framework for inconsistency-tolerant reasoning grounded in the notion of hitting sets of classical interpretations. By defining inference relations based on minimal hitting sets under a range of preference criteria, our approach generalizes and extends classical MCS-based reasoning to a semantic, model-oriented setting. We characterized four distinct inference modes and systematically analyzed their logical properties. Our comparisons with maximal consistent subset inference, Priest’s 3-valued logic, and the KLM postulates demonstrate both the expressive flexibility and the formal rigor of the framework. These results provide a foundation for principled reasoning in inconsistent environments. Some related work on 3-valued hitting set is of Coste-Marquis and Marquis 2008, where three-valued models are utilized to derive consistent two-valued models by systematically forgetting inconsistent information. Future work should examine the computational complexity of these inference relations, explore their deeper connections to other semantic nonmonotonic formalisms, and investigate applications in belief revision (Alchourron, Gärdenfors, and Makinson 1985), formal argumentation (Gabbay, Giacomini, and Simari 2024; Atkinson et al. 2017), and logics that integrate both syntactic and semantic criteria for minimality.

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Appendix

Proposition 1. *Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation and let K be a knowledge base. The following statements hold:*

- *If \prec is well-founded, then $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is non-empty.*
- *Each $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is non-empty.*

Proof. In the following, we show each of the statements.

- Let $\preceq \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a well-founded relation. The set $\mathcal{H}(K)$ is not empty, since you can construct a hitting set $H_\omega = \{\omega \mid \omega \models \phi, \text{ for each } \phi \in K\}$. Because \prec is well-founded then there is a set $T \in S$ for every $S \subseteq 2^\Omega$ such that there is no $T' \in S$ with $T' \prec T$. Definition 9 and the latter property imply that for each K there is a minimal hitting set with respect to \prec .
- Because K is non-empty, there is at least one formula $\phi \in K$. Since every hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ contains a model of ϕ , H is non-empty. \square

Corollary 1. *Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation, let K be a consistent knowledge base, and let ϕ be a formula. If \prec is proper, then $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ns}} \phi$ iff $K \sim_\prec^{\text{nc}} \phi$ iff $K \models \phi$.*

Proof. We first begin by proving that necessary skeptical inference (\sim_\prec^{ns}) and necessary credulous inference (\sim_\prec^{nc}) are equivalent if the knowledge base is consistent.

- “ \Rightarrow ” Assume $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ns}} \phi$. Then, every interpretation $\omega \in H$ in every hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$, $\omega \models \phi$. Adding to that, due to Proposition 1, each $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is not empty and \mathcal{H}_\prec is also non-empty. Hence, there exists an interpretation $\omega \in H$ in every $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ where $\omega \models \phi$, which entails $K \sim_\prec^{\text{nc}} \phi$.
- “ \Leftarrow ” Assume $K \sim_\prec^{\text{nc}} \phi$. This means that in every hitting set there is at-least one model of ϕ . Moreover, since \prec is compatible with classical consistency, then $|H| = 1$ for every $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$. Therefore, $\omega \models \phi$ holds for all interpretations $\omega \in H$, since ω is the only element in H . Hence, we obtain $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ns}} \phi$.

Next, we prove that $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ns}} \phi$ iff $K \models \phi$.

- “ \Rightarrow ” If $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ns}} \phi$ then every interpretation in every hitting set satisfies ϕ . Recall that K is consistent and compatible with classical consistency. Hence, each $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is a singleton. Then, $\{\omega\}$ is a minimal hitting set with ω modeling every formula in K , and $\omega \models \phi$. Therefore, it holds $K \models \phi$.
- “ \Leftarrow ” If $K \models \phi$ then every model of K is a model of ϕ . Moreover, because \prec is compatible with classical consistency, then for each $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$, we have $\omega \in \text{Mod}(K)$. Then, $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ns}} \phi$ holds. \square

Corollary 2. *Let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation, K be a consistent knowledge base, and ϕ a formula. If \prec is proper then $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ps}} \phi$ iff $K \sim_\prec^{\text{pc}} \phi$ iff $K \cup \{\phi\} \not\models \perp$.*

Proof. First we show that possible skeptical inference (\sim_\prec^{ps}) and possible credulous inference (\sim_\prec^{pc}) are equivalent if the knowledge base is consistent. We start by showing $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ps}} \phi$ iff $K \sim_\prec^{\text{pc}} \phi$.

- “ \Rightarrow ” Assume $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ps}} \phi$. Then, for some hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H} - \prec(K)$, where every interpretation $\omega \in H$, it holds $\omega \models \phi$. Adding to that, due to Proposition 1, each $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ is not empty and \mathcal{H}_\prec is also non-empty. Hence, there exists an interpretation $\omega \in H$ in some $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ where $\omega \models \phi$, which entails $K \sim_\prec^{\text{pc}} \phi$.
- “ \Leftarrow ” If $K \sim_\prec^{\text{pc}} \phi$ then some hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ has at-least one interpretation $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$. However, since \prec is compatible with classical consistency, then every minimal hitting set contains a single interpretation. From the earlier observation, one of those interpretations satisfies K and models ϕ . Then, $K \sim_\prec^{\text{ps}} \phi$.

Second part is to prove that $K \sim_\prec^{\text{pc}} \phi$ iff $K \cup \{\phi\} \not\models \perp$.

- “ \Rightarrow ” It holds that $K \sim_\prec^{\text{pc}} \phi$. Moreover, recall that \prec is compatible with classical consistency. Then, there exists an interpretation in some minimal hitting set such that $H = \{\omega\}$ with $\omega \models K$ and $\omega \models \phi$. Consequently $K \cup \{\phi\}$ is consistent.
- “ \Leftarrow ” Let $K \cup \{\phi\} \not\models \perp$ be true. Then, we have that $K \cup \{\phi\}$ is consistent. Thus, there is an interpretation ω such that $\omega \models K$ and $\omega \models \phi$ holds. Therefore, the set $\{\omega\}$ is a hitting set of K . Moreover, since \prec is compatible with classical consistency. Then, $\{\omega\}$ is a minimal hitting set. It follows that there is a $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec$ where $H = \{\omega\}$ and $\omega \models \phi$. Hence, $K \sim_\prec^{\text{pc}} \phi$ holds. \square

Proposition 3. *The relation $\prec_\#$ is proper.*

Proof. We show that the relation $\prec_\#$ is well-founded and compatible with classical consistency.

- The relation $\prec_\#$ is well-founded because for any finite set $X \subseteq 2^\Omega$, $|X| \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Moreover, natural numbers have a minimal number. Then, it holds $\prec_\#$ is well-founded.
- Given a consistent knowledge base K . Let ω be a model of K . Then, $H = \{\omega\}$ is a (minimal) hitting set with $|H| = 1$. For the second part, since $\{\omega\}$ is a hitting set and has cardinality 1, hence any minimal hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\#(K)$ will have $|H| = 1$. \square

Proposition 4. *The relation \prec_{ca} is proper.*

Proof. We prove that \prec_{ca} is proper by showing that it is well-founded and compatible with classical consistency.

1. Let $S \subseteq 2^\Omega$ be some finite set. The number of conflicting atoms for any $X \in S$ is also finite. Hence, S has a lower bound, which gives us \prec_{ca} is well-founded.
2. Given a consistent knowledge base K . Let ω be a model of K . Then, the hitting set $H = \{\omega\}$ is a singleton hitting set, and $CA(H) = \emptyset$. Moreover, for the second part, any other minimal hitting set $H' \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$ must have $CA(H') = \emptyset$, which means $|H'| = 1$. \square

Proposition 5. *The relation \prec_d is proper.*

Proof. We prove that \prec_d is proper by showing that it is well-founded and compatible with classical consistency.

- For any finite set $S \subseteq 2^{\Omega_{\text{At}}}$ the number of atoms is finite. Hence, the distance between them in any set $T \in S$ has a lower bound. Therefore, \prec_d is well-founded.
- Given a consistent knowledge base K . Let ω be a model of K . Then, $H = \{\omega\}$ is a hitting set with $|H| = 1$, and $D(H) = 0$. Therefore, H is minimal. For the second part, any other hitting set $H' \in \mathcal{H}_d(K)$ with $D(H') = 0$ must be a singleton and contain a model of K . \square

Proposition 6. *Let K be a knowledge base, and let $\prec \subseteq 2^{\Omega} \times 2^{\Omega}$ be a well-founded relation. The following relationships among $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}}$, $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}}$, $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}}$, and $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}}$ hold:*

1. If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \phi$, then $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \phi$
2. If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \phi$, then $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi$
3. If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \phi$, then $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi$
4. If $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi$, then $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi$

Proof. We show each statement separately, let ϕ be a formula. Then:

1. Assume $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \phi$. Then, for every $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ and every interpretation $\omega \in H$ it holds that $\omega \models \phi$. Moreover, each $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ is non-empty due to Proposition 1. Then, we obtain $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \phi$.
2. Assume $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \phi$, this means that for every $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ and for every interpretation $\omega \in H$, it holds that $\omega \models \phi$. Moreover, $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ is non-empty from Proposition 1. Then, it must be the case that there is some $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ such that any interpretation $\omega \in H$, it holds that $\omega \models \phi$. Hence, we obtain $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi$.
3. Assume $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \phi$. Then, there exist some interpretation $\omega \in H$ in every hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ such that, it holds $\omega \models \phi$. Furthermore, $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ is non-empty due to Proposition 1. Then it is the case that some interpretations $\omega \in H$ of some $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ where $\omega \models \phi$. Hence, we obtain $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi$.
4. From $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi$, we obtain that for every interpretation $\omega \in H$ in some hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ it holds $\omega \models \phi$. Moreover, each H is non-empty due to Proposition 1. Because of that, there exists a non-empty minimal hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ and some interpretation $\omega \in H$, such that $\omega \models \phi$. This shows that $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi$. \square

Lemma 1. *Let K be a knowledge base and ϕ a formula. Then*

- $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi$ iff $K \not\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \neg \phi$.
- $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi$ iff $K \not\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \neg \phi$.

Proof. We start by showing the first statement. The following sequence of equivalences yields the statement.

$$\begin{aligned} K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \phi &\Leftrightarrow \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \forall \omega \in H : \omega \models \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow \neg \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \forall \omega \in H : \omega \models \neg \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow \neg \forall H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \not\models \neg \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow \neg \forall H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \models \neg \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow K \not\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{nc}} \neg \phi \end{aligned}$$

and similarly for item 2 as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}} \phi &\Leftrightarrow \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \models \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow \neg \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \models \neg \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow \neg \forall H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \forall \omega \in H : \omega \not\models \neg \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow \neg \forall H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) : \forall \omega \in H : \omega \models \neg \phi \\ &\Leftrightarrow K \not\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ns}} \neg \phi \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Proposition 7. *For all $I \in \{\text{ns}, \text{nc}, \text{ps}, \text{pc}\}$, and all $(x, y) \in \{(\#, \text{ca}), (\#, d), (d, \text{ca})\}$, the relations \vdash_x^I and \vdash_y^I are incomparable.*

Proof. We will show that $\vdash_{\#}$ is not comparable with \vdash_{ca} using Example 7.

$$\begin{aligned} \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} & \quad K \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}} \neg r \vee p \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} \neg r \vee p. \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} r \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{ns}} r. \\ \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} & \quad K \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q. \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} \neg p \wedge q \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{nc}} \neg p \wedge q. \\ \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} & \quad K \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}} \neg r \vee p \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} \neg r \vee p. \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} r \wedge s \wedge t \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{ps}} r \wedge s \wedge t. \\ \vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} & \quad K \vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q. \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} \neg p \wedge q \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\#}^{\text{pc}} \neg p \wedge q. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the same inferences show the incomparability of $\vdash_{\#}$ and \vdash_d

The knowledge base $K_3 = \{p \wedge q \wedge r, p \rightarrow q \wedge \neg r, \neg q \wedge \neg r\}$ from Example 6. Is a witness for the incomparability of \vdash_{ca} and \vdash_d such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \vdash_d^{\text{ns}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} & \quad K \vdash_d^{\text{ns}} \neg p \vee q \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} \neg p \vee q \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} \not\subseteq \vdash_d^{\text{ns}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ns}} p \text{ while } K \not\vdash_d^{\text{ns}} p. \\ \vdash_d^{\text{nc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} & \quad K \vdash_d^{\text{nc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q \wedge \neg r \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q \wedge \neg r. \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_d^{\text{nc}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{nc}} q \wedge \neg r \text{ while } K \not\vdash_d^{\text{nc}} q \wedge \neg r. \\ \vdash_d^{\text{ps}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} & \quad K \vdash_d^{\text{ps}} \neg p \vee q \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} \neg p \vee q. \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} \not\subseteq \vdash_d^{\text{ps}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{ps}} p \text{ while } K \not\vdash_d^{\text{ps}} p. \\ \vdash_d^{\text{pc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} & \quad K \vdash_d^{\text{pc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q \wedge \neg r \text{ while } K \not\vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} \neg p \wedge \neg q \wedge \neg r. \\ \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} \not\subseteq \vdash_d^{\text{pc}} & \quad K \vdash_{\text{ca}}^{\text{pc}} q \wedge \neg r \text{ while } K \not\vdash_d^{\text{pc}} q \wedge \neg r. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Proposition 8. *Let K be a knowledge base. Then*

$$\forall M \in \text{MCS}(K) : \exists H \in \mathcal{H}_{\#}(K) : \exists \omega \in H : \omega \models M$$

Proof. By definition of hitting sets from Definition 8, each hitting set must satisfy every formula in the knowledge base, so each interpretation satisfies some formulas in the knowledge base. Therefore, for some hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\#(K)$, let $\omega \in H$ be some interpretation such that $\omega \models \Phi$ and $\Phi \subseteq M$. Since M is consistent, then there must exist an interpretation ω' that satisfies M . However, if we replace ω in H with ω' , that would result in a set H' that is the same size as H , i.e., minimal, and is more general in the sense that it satisfies everything that H satisfies plus previously unsatisfied elements of M . Consequently, H' is a minimal hitting set of K . \square

Theorem 1. *It holds:*

1. $\vdash_\#^{ns} \subseteq \vdash_i^{mc}$
2. $\vdash_w^{mc} \subseteq \vdash_\#^{pc}$

Proof. We show that $\vdash_\#^{ns} \subseteq \vdash_i^{mc}$ holds. It follows from Proposition 8 that all maximally consistent subsets are satisfied by some interpretation in a hitting set. Then assuming the antecedent results in having all interpretations of every hitting set satisfying ϕ . Which shows that all maximally consistent subsets satisfy ϕ . Then we obtain that $K \vdash_i^{mc} \phi$ holds.

We show that $\vdash_w^{mc} \subseteq \vdash_\#^{pc}$ holds. Let $K \vdash_w^{mc} \phi$ hold. From the latter we obtain that there is some maximal consistent subset $M \in MCS(K)$ such that $M \models \phi$ by employing Proposition 8, we obtain that there is a hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\#(K)$ and an interpretation $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models M$. Because $M \models \phi$ holds, we have $\omega \models \phi$. Consequently, we also have $K \vdash_\#^{pc} \phi$.

The strictness of the subset relations is witnessed by Example 1. For $K_3 \vdash_i^{mc} q$ and $K_3 \not\vdash_\#^{ns} q$, and $K_3 \vdash_w^{mc} \neg q$ while $K_3 \not\vdash_\#^{pc} \neg q$. \square

Proposition 9. *Let ϕ be a formula, and v, v' be 3-valued interpretations. For every $v' \sqsubseteq v$ it holds that*

1. *If $v(\phi) = true$, then $v'(\phi) \in \{true, both\}$*
2. *If $v(\phi) = both$, then $v'(\phi) = both$*
3. *If $v(\phi) = false$, then $v'(\phi) \in \{false, both\}$*

Proof. We prove this by induction on the structure of the formula

Base-Case ϕ is an atom, let a be that atom. There are the following cases:

- $v(a) = true$. In that case, $v'(a) \in \{true, both\}$ since $v' \sqsubseteq v$, or
- $v(a) = both$. In that case again $v'(a) = both$ because $v' \sqsubseteq v$, or
- $v(a) = false$. In that case, $v'(a) \in \{both, false\}$

Induction-step Let ϕ be an arbitrary formula with any structure, and let v and v' be two 3-valued interpretations such that $v' \sqsubseteq v$. Then there are the following cases:

1. If $\phi = \neg\psi$ and $v(\phi) = true$: then $v(\psi) = false$ and for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, $v'(\psi) \in \{false, both\}$ by the hypothesis. Hence, $v'(\phi) \in \{true, both\}$
2. If $\phi = \neg\psi$ and $v(\phi) = both$: then $v(\psi) = both$ and for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, $v'(\psi) = both$ by the hypothesis. Hence, $v'(\phi) = both$

3. If $\phi = \neg\psi$ and $v(\phi) = false$: then $v(\psi) = true$ and for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, $v'(\psi) \in \{true, both\}$ by the hypothesis. Hence, $v'(\phi) \in \{false, both\}$

4. If $\phi = \psi \wedge \xi$ and $v(\phi) = true$, then $v(\psi) = true$ and $v(\xi) = true$: Hence, for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, $v'(\psi) \in \{true, both\}$ and $v'(\xi) \in \{true, both\}$ by the hypothesis. Hence, $v'(\phi) \in \{true, both\}$

5. If $\phi = \psi \wedge \xi$ and $v(\phi) = both$, then consider all cases where $v(\phi) = both$ it can be: $v(\psi) = both$ and $v(\xi) = both$, or $v(\psi) = both$ and $v(\xi) = true$, or $v(\psi) = true$ and $v(\xi) = both$ due to Table 1; for each case v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, there are the following cases due to the hypothesis:

- (a) Either $v'(\psi) = both$ and $v'(\xi) = both$
- (b) Or $v'(\psi) = both$ and $v'(\xi) = true$
- (c) or $v'(\psi) = true$ and $v'(\xi) = both$.

In all cases, $v'(\phi) = both$

6. If $\phi = \psi \wedge \xi$ and $v(\phi) = false$: for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, there are 3 cases due to Table 1 and our hypothesis:

- (a) Either $v'(\psi) \in \{false, both\}$ and $v'(\xi) \in \{false, both\}$
- (b) Or $v'(\psi) \in \{true, both\}$ and $v'(\xi) = false$
- (c) or $v'(\psi) = false$ and $v'(\xi) \in \{true, both\}$.

In all cases, $v'(\phi) \in \{false, both\}$

7. If $\phi = \psi \vee \xi$ and $v(\phi) = true$, then consider all cases where $v(\phi) = true$. It can be: $v(\psi) = true$ and $v(\xi) = true$, or $v(\psi) = true$ and $v(\xi) \in \{both, false\}$, or $v(\psi) \in \{both, false\}$ and $v(\xi) = true$ due to Table 1; in all cases, for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, it must follow from the hypothesis that $v'(\psi) \in \{true, both\}$ or $v'(\xi) \in \{true, both\}$. Hence, $v'(\phi) \in \{true, both\}$.

8. If $\phi = \psi \vee \xi$ and $v(\phi) = both$, then consider all cases where $v(\phi) = both$. It can be: $v(\psi) = both$ and $v(\xi) = both$, or $v(\psi) = both$ and $v(\xi) = false$, or $v(\psi) = false$ and $v(\xi) = both$ due to Table 1; in all cases, for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, it must follow from the hypothesis that $v'(\psi) = both$ or $v'(\xi) = both$. Hence, $v'(\phi) = both$.

9. If $\phi = \psi \vee \xi$ and $v(\phi) = false$ then the case where $v(\phi) = false$. It must be that, $v(\psi) = false$ and $v(\xi) = false$, due to Table 1; in that case, for any v' with $v' \sqsubseteq v$, it must follow from the hypothesis that $v'(\psi) \in \{false, both\}$ or $v'(\xi) \in \{false, both\}$ by the hypothesis. Hence, $v'(\phi) \in \{false, both\}$. \square

Proposition 10. *Let K be a knowledge base. Then for all $H \in \mathcal{H}(K)$, $v_H \models^3 K$.*

Proof. For each $\phi \in K$ and $H \in \mathcal{H}(K)$, there is $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$. Furthermore, Since the maximal element in the information order is two valued interpretations, then $v_H \sqsubseteq \omega$. Therefore, by Proposition 9 $v_H \models^3 \phi$. Thus, $v_H \models^3 K$. \square

Proposition 11. *Let v be a 3-val interpretation, and let ϕ be a formula. It holds that $v \models^3 \phi$ iff $v \models^3 \phi'$, where ϕ' is the equivalent conjunctive normal form of ϕ*

Proof. The 3-valued satisfaction relation \models^3 is defined via truth tables in Figure 1 for the connectives \neg, \wedge, \vee . The transformation to conjunctive normal form relies on the following equivalences:

- Double negation: $\neg\neg\phi \equiv^3 \phi$.
- DeMorgan rule: $\neg(\phi \vee \psi) \equiv^3 \neg\phi \wedge \neg\psi$, and $\neg(\phi \wedge \psi) \equiv^3 \neg\phi \vee \neg\psi$.
- Distributivity: $\phi \vee (\psi \wedge \xi) \equiv^3 (\phi \vee \psi) \wedge (\phi \vee \xi)$, and dually $\phi \wedge (\psi \vee \xi) \equiv^3 (\phi \wedge \psi) \vee (\phi \wedge \xi)$.

Each of these equivalences is preserved under \models^3 ; this can be verified directly using the truth tables. Since CNF transformation is composed entirely of such equivalence steps, and \models^3 respects each of them, it follows that ϕ and its CNF form ϕ' are equivalent under \models^3 . \square

Lemma 2. *Let ϕ be a disjunction of literals and v a 3-valued interpretation with $v \models^3 \phi$. Then there is $\omega \in H_v$ with $\omega \models \phi$.*

Proof. Since $v \models^3 \phi$ and $\phi = l_1 \vee l_2 \vee l_3 \dots \vee l_n$, then there are two cases

1. Either $v(\phi) = \text{true}$. In that case, there is a literal $l_i \in \{l_1, \dots, l_n\}$ such that $v(l_i) = \text{true}$. Which means that there is an interpretation $\omega \in H_v$ such that $\omega(l_i) = \text{true}$. Hence, $\omega \models \phi$
2. Or $v(\phi) = \text{both}$. In that case, there exists a literal $l_i \in \{l_1, \dots, l_n\}$ such that $v(l_i) = \text{both}$, which means that there are 2 interpretations $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in H_v$ such that $\omega_1(l_i) = \text{true}$ and $\omega_2(l_i) = \text{false}$. Hence, we have $\omega_1 \models \phi$. \square

Proposition 12. *Let K be a knowledge base in CNF, where $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses and v a 3-valued interpretation. If $v \models^3 K$ then $H_v \in \mathcal{H}(K)$.*

Proof. $v \models^3 K$ entails that $v \models^3 \phi$ for every $\phi \in K$. Moreover, from Lemma 2 for each ϕ where $v \models^3 \phi$, there is $\omega \in H_v$ where $\omega \models \phi$. Hence, $H_v \in \mathcal{H}(K)$. \square

Proposition 13. *Let K be a knowledge base in CNF, where $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses, and $v \in \text{MinMod}^3(K)$, then $H_v \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$.*

Proof. This is proven by contradiction. Assume $v \in \text{MinMod}^3(K)$ and $H_v \notin \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$. Then, from Proposition 12, $H_v \in \mathcal{H}(K)$. Hence, there exists a hitting set H' where $H' \in \mathcal{H}$ and $CA(H') \subsetneq CA(H_v)$, using Definition 20, construct $v_{H'}$. Keeping in mind that, $v_{H'} \models^3 K$ (by Proposition 10) and $v_{H'}^{-1}(\text{both}) = CA(H')$ (from Observation 2). However, that would mean that $v_{H'}^{-1}(\text{both}) \subsetneq v^{-1}(\text{both})$ since $v^{-1}(\text{both}) = CA(H_v)$ (from Observation 3). Hence, $v \notin \text{MinMod}^3(K)$ which is a contradiction. \square

Proposition 14. *Let K be a knowledge base in CNF, where $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses. For each $H \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$, then $v_H \in \text{MinMod}^3(K)$.*

Proof. Similar to Proposition 13. This is proven by contradiction. Assume the contrary that $H \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$ and $v_H \notin \text{MinMod}^3(K)$. Then, from Proposition 10, $v_H \models^3 K$. Hence, there exists a v' where $v' \in \text{MinMod}^3$ and v' contains less atoms assigned to *both* than v_H . Then, using Definition 22, construct $H_{v'}$ such that $H_{v'} \in \mathcal{H}(K)$ (by Proposition 12) and $v'^{-1}(\text{both}) = CA(H_{v'})$ (from Observation 3). However, that would mean that $CA(H_{v'}) \subsetneq CA(H)$ since $v_H^{-1}(\text{both}) = CA(H)$ (from Observation 2). Hence, $H \notin \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$ which is a contradiction. \square

Theorem 2. *Let K be a knowledge base such that $K = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ and C_1, \dots, C_n are clauses. $K \models^3 \phi$ iff $K \sim_{ca}^{\text{nc}} \phi$*

Proof. We show $K \models^3 \phi$ iff $K \sim_{ca}^{\text{nc}} \phi$ by showing both directions.

“ \Rightarrow ” We first show that $K \models^3 \phi$ entails $K \sim_{ca}^{\text{nc}} \phi$, so assume that $K \models^3 \phi$ holds. In order to show $K \sim_{ca}^{\text{nc}} \phi$, we have to show that for all $H \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$ there is $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$. So let $H \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$ be arbitrary. Due to Proposition 14 we have $v_H \in \text{MinMod}^3(K)$ and therefore $v_H \models^3 \phi$ (due to $K \models^3 \phi$). By Lemma 1 we have that there is $\omega \in H_{v_H} = H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$.

“ \Leftarrow ” Then We show that $K \sim_{ca}^{\text{nc}} \phi$ entails $K \models^3 \phi$. Assume the antecedent $K \sim_{ca}^{\text{nc}} \phi$. In order to show the consequent $K \models^3 \phi$, we have to show that for all $v \in \text{MinMod}^3(K)$ $v \models^3 \phi$. so let v be an arbitrary 3-valued interpretation in $\text{MinMod}^3(K)$. Due to Proposition 13 we have $H_v \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$. Therefore, there is an interpretation $\omega \in H_v$, where $\omega \models \phi$ (due to $K \sim_{ca}^{\text{nc}} \phi$), and hence $v_{H_v} = v \models^3 \phi$. \square

Proposition 15. *Let K be a knowledge base, let ϕ be a formula, and let $\prec \subseteq 2^\Omega \times 2^\Omega$ be a relation. If there is a hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ with $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$. Then, there is no $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$, and $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K \cup \{\phi\})$.*

Proof. Assume the contrary, i.e., $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ with $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$ and there is a hitting set $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$. Note that H' is also a hitting of K . Hence, H' witnesses that H is not an element of $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$. This contradicts our initial assumption of $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$. Hence, there is no $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$. Consequently, Assume the contrary, i.e., $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ with $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$ and there is a hitting set $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$. Note that H' is also a hitting of K . Hence, H' witnesses that H is not an element of $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$. This contradicts our initial assumption of $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$. Hence, there is no $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$. Consequently, Assume the contrary, i.e., $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$ with $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \phi$ and there is a hitting set $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$. Note that H' is also a hitting of K . Hence, H' witnesses that H is not an element of $\mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$. This contradicts our initial assumption of $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K)$. Hence, there is no $H' \in \mathcal{H}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $H' \prec H$. Consequently, it holds that $H \in \mathcal{H}_\prec(K \cup \{\phi\})$. \square

Proposition 16. Let $\prec \in \{\prec_{\#}, \prec_{ca}, \prec_d\}$. It holds \prec is regular.

Proof. We prove the statement for each relation.

1. We start with showing that $\prec_{\#}$ is *regular*. Towards a contradiction, assume the contrary. It holds $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\phi\}) \not\subseteq \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ while having some $H_{\phi} \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ with $\omega_{\phi} \models \phi$ such that $\omega_{\phi} \models \phi$. Therefore, Let H, H' be minimal hitting sets (of K and $K \cup \{\phi\}$) such that $H' \notin \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$, leading to $|H'| < |H|$. Clearly, because H' is a hitting set of $K \cup \{\phi\}$, it is also a hitting set of K . Furthermore, we know that $|H| = |H_{\phi}|$ from the antecedent. Hence, we get that $|H'| < |H| = |H_{\phi}|$. By employing Proposition 15, we know that there is no $H^* \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $|H^*| < |H_{\phi}|$. Hence, a contradiction, since $H' \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ and $|H'| < |H|$.
2. We show that \prec_{ca} is *regular* by contradiction. Let $H_{\phi} \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ be such that $\omega_{\phi} \in H$ and $\omega_{\phi} \models \phi$ holds. Assume $H' \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ and $H' \notin \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$. There are three cases to consider. The first case is that H' is not a hitting set of K . That is clearly false, since $H' \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K \cup \{\phi\})$. Therefore, it must model every formula in K . In the second case, H' is incomparable to hitting sets of $\mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$. Then, there is a formula $\psi \in K$ with no model $\omega \in H'$ where $\omega \models \psi$, which is false. The third case is that H' is not minimal. This means that there is some $H \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K)$ with $CA(H') \subsetneq CA(H)$. However, that is a contradiction to Proposition 15 because $CA(H_{\phi}) = CA(H)$, and there is no $H^* \in \mathcal{H}_{ca}(K \cup \{\phi\})$ with $CA(H^*) \subsetneq H_{\phi}$.
3. The relation \prec_d is *Regular*. The proof is identical to $\prec_{\#}$ by replacing the modulus operator of any hitting set $|H|$ with the distance function $D(H)$. \square

Proposition 17. Let K be a knowledge base, let ϕ be a consistent formula, and let $\prec \subseteq 2^{\Omega} \times 2^{\Omega}$ be a regular relation. If a minimal hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ contains a model of ϕ , then $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\phi\}) \subseteq \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$.

Proof. This follows directly from Definition 23 of a regular relation. \square

Theorem 3. Let $\prec \subseteq 2^{\Omega} \times 2^{\Omega}$ be a regular proper relation. Then:

- $\vdash_{\prec}^{ns}, \vdash_{\prec}^{nc}, \vdash_{\prec}^{ps}$ and \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} satisfy reflexivity, right weakening, left logical equivalence, cut, or, and rational monotony.
- $\vdash_{\prec}^{ns}, \vdash_{\prec}^{nc}$ satisfy CM
- $\vdash_{\prec}^{ps}, \vdash_{\prec}^{pc}$ violate CM

Proof. We first show the postulates that are satisfied by every inference relation. The analysis below walks through each postulate individually

- (Ref) The relations' \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} and \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} satisfaction of (Ref) follows from Corollary 1 and satisfaction of (Ref) by classical propositional logic. For \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} and \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} satisfaction of (Ref) follows from Corollary 2 directly.

(RW) Note that we have that $\phi \models \psi$ holds if $\text{Mod}(\phi) \subseteq \text{Mod}(\psi)$ holds. From this, and the definition of $\vdash_{\prec}^{ns}, \vdash_{\prec}^{nc}, \vdash_{\prec}^{ps}$ and \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} , we obtain that $K \vdash \phi$ implies $K \vdash \psi$ for all $\vdash \in \{\vdash_{\prec}^{ns}, \vdash_{\prec}^{nc}, \vdash_{\prec}^{ps}, \vdash_{\prec}^{pc}\}$.

(LLE) For any relation $\vdash \in \{\vdash_{\prec}^{ns}, \vdash_{\prec}^{nc}, \vdash_{\prec}^{ps}, \vdash_{\prec}^{pc}\}$ and satisfaction of (LLE) follows directly from Definition 24.

(Cut) We show the satisfaction of cut in two steps.

\vdash_{\prec}^{ns} and \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} Let \vdash be one of \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} or \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} in the following. Assume that $K \vdash \alpha$ and $K \cup \{\alpha\} \vdash^{ns} \beta$ holds. From $K \vdash \alpha$, we obtain that every minimal hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ contains a model of α . Note that due to Proposition 1, $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ is non-empty, hence, such an H is also guaranteed to exist. Then, by employing Proposition 17, we obtain from the observations above that each minimal hitting set H of K is also a minimal hitting set of $K \cup \{\alpha\}$, which implies that $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) = \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\alpha\})$ holds. Consequently, we have that $K \cup \{\alpha\} \vdash \beta$ implies that $K \vdash \beta$ holds.

\vdash_{\prec}^{ps} and \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} We will give the proof for \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} . The proof for \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} is analogue, but H_{β} is a minimal hitting set that contains a model of β . From $K \vdash^{ps} \alpha$, we obtain that there is minimal hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ of K that contains only models of α . Note that due to Proposition 1, we obtain that H a non-empty set. Consequently, H contains at least one model of α . Moreover, from $K \cup \{\alpha\} \vdash^{ps} \beta$, we obtain that there is a minimal hitting set $H_{\beta} \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\alpha\})$ contains only models of β . By employing Proposition 17 and our observations from above, we obtain $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\alpha\}) \subseteq \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$. Consequently, H_{β} is also a hitting set of K . Consequently, we obtain that $K \vdash^{ps} \beta$ holds.

(Or) Regarding \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} and \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} satisfaction of (Or). Let \vdash either be \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} or \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} . Note that (Or) is satisfied by entailment \models of classical propositional logic. Consequently, due to Corollary 1, (Or) is also satisfied by \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} . $\{\psi \vee \phi\}$ is consistent when ϕ or ψ is consistent.

For \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} and \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} . Let \vdash either be \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} or \vdash_{\prec}^{pc} . Assume that $\{\phi\} \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} \chi$ and $\{\psi\} \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} \chi$ hold. By employing Corollary 2, our assumptions are equivalent to stating that $\{\phi, \chi\}$ is consistent and, respectively, that $\{\psi, \chi\}$ is consistent. This also implies that $\{\phi \vee \psi, \chi\}$ is consistent. By employing Corollary 2 again, the latter yields $\{\phi \vee \psi\} \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} \chi$.

(RM) We show the Postulate (RM) for \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} . However, the proof steps are analogous with every other inference relation. Let $K \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} \phi$ and $K \not\vdash_{\prec}^{ns} \psi$. By employing Lemma 1, we obtain $K \vdash_{\prec}^{ps} \psi$ from $K \not\vdash_{\prec}^{ns} \psi$. Therefore, there exists a hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ with $\omega \in H$ such that $\omega \models \psi$. Then, from Proposition 17, we get $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\psi\}) \subseteq \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ because \prec is regular. Furthermore, Note that for every $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ and for every $\omega \in H$ it holds $\omega \models \phi$. Consequently, because of $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\psi\}) \subseteq \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$, for every $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\psi\})$ and for every $\omega \in H$ we have $\omega \models \phi$. Hence, $K \cup \{\psi\} \vdash^{ns} \phi$

Next, we show that \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} and \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} satisfy (CM). Let \vdash be one of \vdash_{\prec}^{ns} or \vdash_{\prec}^{nc} . Assume that $K \vdash \alpha$ and $K \vdash \beta$ holds. From

$K \vdash \alpha$, we obtain that every minimal hitting set $H \in \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ contain a model of α and a model of β . Note that due to Proposition 1, $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K)$ is not empty, hence, such an H is also guaranteed to exist. By employing Proposition 17, we obtain from the observations above that each minimal hitting set H of K is also a minimal hitting set of $K \cup \{\alpha\}$. Our observations imply that $\mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) = \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\alpha\})$ holds. Consequently, we have that $K \cup \{\alpha\} \vdash \beta$ holds.

As last step of this proof, we show that $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}}$ and $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}}$ violate (CM). We give a counter example to show the proof for the violation of (CM) by $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}}$ with $\prec \in \{\prec_{\#}, \prec_{ca}, \prec_d\}$. The proof for $\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{pc}}$ is the same, but with $\beta = p \wedge q \wedge \neg r$. Let $K = \{p \wedge q \wedge r, p \wedge (q \leftrightarrow \neg r)\}$, let $\alpha = \neg q \wedge r$ and let $\beta = p \wedge q$. The minimal hitting sets of K , respectively $K \cup \{\alpha\}$, are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K) &= \{H_1, H_2\} & \text{with } H_1 &= \{pqr, pq\bar{r}\} \\ \mathcal{H}_{\prec}(K \cup \{\alpha\}) &= \{H_2\} & H_2 &= \{pqr, p\bar{q}r\} \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have that $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \alpha$ and $K \vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \beta$ holds. However, H_2 contains no models of β . Thus, we obtain that $K \cup \{\alpha\} \not\vdash_{\prec}^{\text{ps}} \beta$ holds; which witnesses a violation of (CM). \square